

Table 2. Resistance of rice cultivars (lines) to 7 pathogenic groups of BB in China 21 d after inoculation.

Variety (line)	Reaction ^a to pathogenic group							Origin	Use
	I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII		
Milyang 23	1	5	3	5	3	5	5	Korea	Hybridization
DV85	5	7	3	3	1	5	3	Bangladesh	Hybridization
IR54	3	3	3	3	5	3	3	IRRI	Hybridization
IRBB 7	3	1	1	1	3	1	1	IRRI	Resistance source
BR568-15-4-2-2-3	3	3	3	1	3	3	3	Bangladesh	Resistance source
C702015	1	3	3	3	3	3	5	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
C722355	1	3	3	5	5	3	3	Taiwan (China)	Resistance source
Suwon	3391333351							Korea	Resistance source

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice scale 0-9.

regions of the northern part beyond the Yangtze River. *Xa-3*, *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, *Xa-6*, or *Xa-7* resistance sources are best in indica-japonica rice cropping regions along the

Yangtze River. *Xa-4*, *xa-5*, and *Xa-7* resistance sources are needed in indica rice cropping regions in the south China coastal area. □

Resistance to tungro in some wild relatives of rice

N. Kobayashi, R. Ikeda, and D. A. Vaughan, IRRI; and S. Shigenaga, Kyoto University, Japan

We tested 16 accessions of wild rice *Oryza* spp. for antibiosis to green leafhopper (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens*. Distant, resistance to rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) infection, and tolerance for tungro.

To test for antibiosis, a 10-d-old seedling of each accession was placed in a test tube with five GLH nymphs (2d instar), with 10 replications. Antibiosis of each accession was rated on a 1-5 scale by counting surviving GLH nymphs every day for 3 d. Those same seedlings (15-d-old) were inoculated with 10 viruliferous GLH adults/seedling for 4 h. Leaves were individually sampled 3 wk after inoculation, and tested for RTBV and RTSV by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. Disease severity of each accession was scored at 4 wk after

Reactions of wild species of rice to GLH and tungro disease.

Genome	Species	IRGC acc. no.	Origin	Anti-biosis to GLH ^a	Plants tested (no.)	Infected plants ^b (%)			Average severity ^c
						B+S	B	S	
AA	<i>O. nivara</i>	102463	Bangladesh	5	38	74	26	0	3
		102175	India	1	18	0	78	0	5
		105333	India	1	49	2	59	0	2
		105409	Sri Lanka	5	39	69	18	3	2
		105417	Sri Lanka	4	18	50	11	6	2
BB	<i>O. punctata</i>	105456	Sri Lanka	4	3	67	33	0	5
		103896	Tanzania	1	17	0	53	0	2
BBCC	<i>O. minuta</i>	105158	Kenya	2	49	0	37	0	3
		101126	Philippines	1	20	5	50	0	3
CC	<i>O. eichingeri</i>	101141	Philippines	1	36	0	56	0	5
		105414	Sri Lanka	2	47	47	43	0	5
CC	<i>O. officinalis</i>	105365	Thailand	1	27	0	0	0	2
		105394	China	3	32	9	81	0	3/7 ^d
CC	<i>O. rhizomatis</i>	105660	Sri Lanka	1	13	15	31	8	5
		105448	Sri Lanka		4	50	25	0	3
CCDD	<i>O. latifolia</i>	100914	Mexico	1	23	57	0	13	3
AA	<i>O. sativa</i> (check varieties)	ARC11554	India	1	54	2	39	0	3
		Utri Merah	Indonesia	5	54	2	52	0	3
		TN1	Taiwan	5	53	96	4	0	9
		IR22	Philippines	5	57	90	10	0	9

^aScale of 1 (resistant) to 5 (susceptible). ^bInfected with both RTBV and RTSV (B+S), with RTSV (S), or with RTBV (B). ^cScale 1 (no symptoms) to 9 (more than 50% plant height reduction and yellow to orange leaf discoloration), using Nasanuddin et al scale.

^dSegregating.

inoculation.

One accession of *O. officinalis* (105365) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to both RTBV and RTSV infection (see table). Two accessions of *O. nivara* (102175, 105333), two of *O. punctata* (103896, 105158), and two of *O. minuta* (101126, 101141) showed high antibiosis to GLH and resistance to RTSV infection. Even with low antibiosis to GLH and severe infection with RTBV and RTSV, three accessions of *O. nivara* (102463, 105409, 105417) showed low scores for symptom severity, indicating tolerance for tungro.

These results suggest that a number of new sources of resistance to both RTBV and RTSV may be found among the wild rices. □

Distribution of rice varieties resistant to bacterial blight (BB) in Yunnan, China

Chen Yong and Xinhua Liao, Yunnan Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Kunming 650205; Yuefeng Xie and Duanpin Zhang, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuchang, China

We screened 4,091 Yunnan rice varieties for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* strain Jiangling 691: 6% were resistant, 84% were susceptible, and 10% were moderately resistant. The frequency of resistance differed within rice classifications (Table 1).

Resistance was more frequent among glutinous rices.

Table 2 shows more resistant varieties among japonica-irrigated-glutinous, japonica-irrigated-nonglutinous, and japonica-upland-glutinous rices. Mean

Table 1. Distribution of BB-resistant rices in Yunnan, China.

Classification	Varieties tested (no.)	Resistant varieties	
		no.	%
Indica	2186	83	3.8
Japonica	1905	159	8.4
Irrigated	3233	202	6.2
Upland	858	40	4.7
Nonglutinous	3183	159	5.0
Glutinous	908	83	9.1